

The Abject Refugee: Displacement, Violence, and the Ethics of Recognition in Post-Partition Bengal — A Literary Representation of Selected Stories

Abstract

The present paper seeks to explore the enduring impact of the Partition of 1947 on the collective memory and socio-political dynamics in Bengal, particularly focusing on the experiences of Hindu refugees forced to migrate from East Pakistan to West Bengal. The Partition unleashed a tumultuous era marked by communal violence and forced migration, severing emotional, cultural, and spatial ties of people from their native lands. Drawing on literary and historical perspectives, the study examines how the memory of Partition is constructed and contested through narratives that challenge dominant historical accounts. It emphasizes the role of memoryscapes in reshaping identities and creating a sense of belonging among refugees, who navigate between their ancestral homes and adopted lands. Furthermore, the analysis delves into the concept of social abjection, as refugees are marginalized and treated as "waste objects" by the state apparatus, impacting their social integration and sense of self. Through textual analysis of literary works like Bashabi Fraser's "Bengal Partition Stories", the study reveals how refugees' experiences are depicted, often highlighting themes of displacement, trauma, and resilience amidst socio-political turmoil. By examining these narratives, the study contributes to understanding the complexities of post-national identities and the enduring legacy of Partition on the Eastern borderlands.

Key Words: Bengal Partition, abjection, refugee, trauma, memoryscapes

Introduction

The Partition unleashed immense suffering, oppression, and injustice upon those who were forced to migrate due to communal violence. Many fled their homes, leaving behind everything they knew, and carried with them the traumatic experiences of violence and loss. These memories are indelibly etched in their minds, haunting them and preventing them from forgetting

the horrors they witnessed. The sudden announcement and subsequent implementation of Partition led to a breakdown in relationships between Hindus and Muslims. What was once a cultural and social fabric woven together regardless of caste or religion now became torn apart by hatred, violence, and distrust. The rivers Ganga and Padma, which once symbolized unity, now marked stark divides between communities. The Partition resulted in the formation of two separate nation-states, India and Pakistan, out of a shared cultural geography. The drawing of the Radcliffe Line, which demarcated the borders, not only separated physical territories but also severed emotional, cultural, and spatial ties that people had with their native lands. Ranabir Samaddar's observation is poignant — the Partition marked a shift from nationalist secularism towards communalism and separatism. This shift fuelled jingoism and mimetic violence on both sides of the newly formed borders, exacerbating tensions and creating a volatile atmosphere where people questioned their sense of belonging. The reference to "Dover Beach's" famous line—"Ignorant armies clash by the night" from Matthew Arnold's poem that underscores the confusion and turmoil caused by the conflict between Science and religion in the Victorian period finds its resonance in the partition ravaged society in which people are killing people. These lines evoke a sense of loss, uncertainty, and a search for meaning amidst chaos. The Partition of India and the creation of Pakistan left a deep scar on the collective psyche of the people involved. It reshaped relationships, identities, and landscapes, leaving a legacy of pain, division, and ongoing reconciliation efforts.

Rewriting History

Urvashi Butalia mentions in her book *The Other side of Silence* that one cannot understand what Partition is about “ Unless we look at how people remember it”(13). In fact, the process of remembering is associated with the concept of rewriting alternative history. Because remembering is a process in which true facts and imagination are intermeshed together, unraveling a plethora of small narratives having no existence in the official history of Partition. Infact, while nation-state is meticulous in silencing painful history in favour of a coercive and absolutist celebration of independence, Urvashi Butalia tries to represent the unheard voices or oral history in which historical events are intermingled with personal

emotion, the past incidents are forced to contemporize with the present. Question arises regarding the omission or addition of the facts made by the Historians. She cites many instances in this connection, of which Mangal Singh's example is very interesting. Although Mangal Singh killed seventeen wives including children but his work has been glorified as martyrdom. The partition history has a canonical metanarrative that precludes alternative versions or proliferation of history, because proliferation always posits a threat to the order. 'Always Historicise' as Fredric Jameson refers to in his *The Political Unconscious* becomes a slogan and the word 'always' is supposed to be inimical to the formation of heterogeneous voices which dehumanized or subaltern voices ask for. The voices which remain hidden in the official history of Partition come to the lime light, while the Postmodern Historiography appears. Louis Montrose mentions two ways to interpret history : 'historicity of the text' and 'textuality of history'. Historicity of the text suggests how history determines the text, on the other hand, textuality of history demands readers participation in delving deep into the history and excavate the minor voices from the debris of silence. Hence, the more we will decipher the textuality of history, the more we will discover how historical representations are contingent like language in general. It helps people comprehend how community and culture are constructed in certain ways. And literary narratives always look at history with new perspective, and thus challenge the credibility of representation. The dialectical relationship between literary representation and history contains within it enormous possibilities. It makes us realize the intertextual resonance between a fictive history and a textualised history as it casts a long shadow over the literary discourse in Bengal, on both sides of the border. The present analysis seeks to point out how the Partition of 1947 has darkened the post-national realities in Eastern border and borderlands. I have taken up few stories from Bashabi Frazer's edited volume *Bengal Partition Stories: An Unclosed Chapter* in an attempt to show how emigrants are reduced to objects and stripped off their human rights, and thus revealing the ontological question of their states of 'being' and 'belonging'.

Memoryscape

Refugees sought to link up between the city in which they were living and their abandoned homelands by taking recourse to imagination. It thus disrupts the physical boundaries as created by the nation-state. Memoryscape being the vital trope generates a porosity in the manufactured border. Those who have experienced the Partition, are fond of ruminating their memories

ingrained in Partition. It can be described through the lens of Cartesian concept of 'res-cogians' (I think, therefore I am) and 'res-extensa' (extended thing does not think). The refugees though may be physically displaced but their minds are in their 'bari' (ancestral homeland now East Pakistan). Hence, they proclaim, "I think, therefore I am". The continuity of consciousness stemming from their past pushes them to re-create their mini home/ 'basha' within the host land (West Bengal). There are two Bengali words for refugee, Saranarhi, which means literally someone who wants to have refuge and protection; and Udvastu, meaning somebody who is homeless but homeless in a particular sense. In fact, home carries a different connotation. The word 'Vastu' is used here to refer to home, which is a Sanskrit word of Vedic vintage. In Bengal, the word is often combined with the word 'bhite', a word connected to the Sanskrit word 'bhitti' meaning foundation. One's permanent home is where one's foundation is. The Bengali language has made this sense of distinction between a temporary place of residence and one's foundational home. "No matter one spends in the place, basha, as Dipesh Chakroborty says, is a temporary place of residence, and one's sense of belonging is transient. Bari is, on the other hand, where one's ancestors have lived for generation" (114). So, the loss which the refugees carry within themselves appears to be acute while they experience similar natural and cultural surroundings in the West Bengal on a regular basis like that of their homeland, East Pakistan. It indicates the process of 'anamnesia' which tends them to conform to the 'cult of mourning'. It usually emanates from their deplorable condition in relation to their proper identity. The universal question like 'who are you' and 'where are you from' pushes them to the word of abyss in which the states of their being and belonging are the vital issues to be taken into account. In fact, the nostalgia and the longing for their own lost homeland tend to formulate collective memories of the refugees in order to avoid the historical reality of the divided lands. Anusua Ray Chaudhuri shows how the refugees in the Post-partition phase attempt to deploy their own survival mechanism through their memory in a unique way; fusing of spaces and places together. The refugees' inclination to cling to imagination is an attempt to reconstitute their own space against the state apparatus. It leads towards a deterritorialization that constructs their host country as a 'heterotopia'.

Social Abjection: Understanding refugees as 'Waste objects'

Socio-Political turmoil that occurred in 1950s onwards, forced a large number of Hindu families to migrate to Calcutta out of religious persecution. As a matter of fact, Calcutta was teeming with population and the Government of West Bengal in tandem with the Government of India extended their helping hands to the refugees so that they could attain their camps and get the proper aids for their livelihoods. But the number of refugees was increasing in such a way that not only generated a climate crisis but also economic and social crisis. Government consequently paid a deaf ear to the refugees (1950-51). It led the refugees to take their responsibility on their own. So they started erecting their camps and thus forged their habitations in the suburbs of Kolkata.

Abjection is a concept by Julia Kristeva which mainly indicates the segregation of child from the mother's body and leads the child towards Lacanian symbolic stage. It defines the path of maturity of a child. Abjection dwells on the psychoanalytic process that generates a relative connection between mother's body or homeland and the hostland. Kristeva writes,

The place of abjection is where meaning collapses, the place where I am not. The abject threatens life, it must be radically excluded from the place of the living subject, propelled away from the body and deposited on the other side of an imaginary border which separates the self from that which threatens the self.(65)

If the condition of the refugees can be analysed through the lens of abjection, it reveals how the very concept of abjection gives birth to two conflicting emotions among the refugees: to live as others and live with others. At the announcement of Partition, the homeland (East Pakistan) becomes other to the Hinduees. They are aware that they are to leave their country as it is no longer theirs and they are to start their journey towards West Bengal, an unknown destination. Hence, they confront alienation on both side of the border, and thereby producing an ambivalent position like 'forever foreigner syndrome'. However, Imogen Tyler revises Kristeva's theory of Abjection by expanding its position from psychoanalysis to historical, political and social axis. Abjection to Tyler is a social force that forges a correlation between society and states through including forms of exclusion. Social abjection operates in relation to Governmentality(such as Citizenship and border control regime) and impacts on particular groups like refugees. Tyler in his book *Revoltng Subjects* seeks to showcase how states of being and states of belonging are usually gone through the process of making and unmaking(Butler and Spivak). He further deploys Bataille's concept of 'Social abjection' in his book in order to point out two states: Subjectivity and Sovereignty together. Social abjection relies in the threshold of body and body

politic. As Bataille implies that abjection defines the violent exclusionary forces of Sovereign power: those forces that rob people of their human dignity and reproduce them as “dehumanized waste , the disposable dregs and refuse of social life”(Tylor 11).The refugees are “disinherited from the possibility of being human”(ibid). Waste population are in this way excluded through their inclusion that abjection usually refers to. Drew Leder in his phenomenological study of ill bodies argues that in the period of illness or sickness, one experiences body as ‘dys-appeared’. He opines “the lived body is how one comes to be in the world but also the mode through which the world comes to be” (25). The refugee is made to see him or herself as an undesirable body as a refugee needs to conform to ‘the norms of intelligibility’ in the receiving society which causes the self to be experienced as a ‘dys-appeared’ one. Such social abjection deems them as waste objects and simultaneously legitimises the existence of their power structure. Having gone through this social abjection, refugees have a chance to express their revolutionary zeal to abjection in a collective way.

Textual Analysis

At the advent of Partition, society moves on under the cauldron of hatred and violence. Religious bifurcation is at the core of the society which conduces the conflictual relationship between Hindu and Muslim. In the story ‘A Thorn in the Path’ by Ramesh Chandra Sen, it is overt how hinduees including men and women remain hidden in the forest out of the fear of oppression of Muslims while Partition was announced. Two importat characters in the story like Jadav and Mohini,his mother, hide themselves in the forest in order to protect themselves from the onslaught of the Muslim tyrants. Hence, they had to run away from one forest to another like that of animals. So, their birth place becomes ‘inhabitable’ or ‘other’ to them. They all of a sudden become strangers in their own country. Terror, intolerance, distrust loom large in the West-Bengal and it pushes them to go to the West-Bengal. On the other side of the border, same situation prevails. The process of otherization comes into prominence due to religious division as designed by Radcliff line. Hinduees belonging to their home country are thought to be aliens and are bound to set out for another location like West Bengal. This is what can be termed as , to put into the words of Kristeva, ‘Abjection’. Abjection is a concept that occurs while there is a breakdown between Self and Other. It is a crucial phase of human individual for one’s development into an independent human being. As per abjection, there is no demarcation

between self and other, hence, Hinduees think of the serenity of the natural surrounding and a feeling of togetherness on the onehand, and on the otherhand, they bear a feeling of affliction in their mind as they are aware of their departure from their homeland. Such conflicting emotion refers to a kind of horror inherent in human experience and existence. Horror is not simply an external concept of genre, but an inherent part of human experience. While many Hindu families start their journey towards West Bengal, feel their toil and helplessness in ever-dewindling world of humanity. Hindu refugees, men and women both are afraid of being attacked by Ansars or Muslims. A vicious atmosphere of distrust is prevalent on both sides of the border. Only children in the story have nothing to do with such fear. The writer seems to showcase through the portrayal of his children characters as to how they remain unperturbed by the perpetuation of divisive mechanism. So, they have been found in the story laughing at the prospect of being attacked by the Muslims, and thereby proclaiming, ‘Anthal Anthal’. So, in the story, we find while Muslims on the otherside is approaching to the hindu refugees with the slogan ‘Alla ho’, it causes a fear to them. Instead of doing any harm to any hindu refugee, Muslims express their mutual empathy to each other. Desipte the religious intolerance, neither Hindu nor Muslim show their vengeance against each other: “Alla ho” has not been replaced by “Jai Hind”. Both of the communities were sad in relation to their impending otherness stemming from their host country. Hence, silence looms large for a while and the so called manufactured social abjection by the state apparatus pushes them to ponder over their own confrontations, paradoxs and ultimately their understanding of self as well as otherness.

The perennial condition of the refugees as, to quote Kristeva, “live with others” and “live as others” is evident in the story. The seven families with whom Parashar starts his journey along with his ailing son, Jadav and his wife, Mohini, have discovered differences or otherisation within the Bengali Hindu Community. There are references to casteism between the fellow community members. Mohini is appaled at showing the condition of her ailing son, Jadav. While Kumudini has asked her to eat with them, the question of casteism crops up. Mohini glanced to her husband and said,

Ghatak replied “ We are Tentule Bicha”

What? We have never really heard of ‘Tentule Bicha’

Oh we are fellow caste people. You can safely have food made by us.

You are joking aren't you? Parashar said

'Stop it, father'. Pratap snubbed. It's still the same old concern about Caste. When are we going to feel ashamed of ourselves (Sen 264).

The society is laden with casteism. More importantly it refers to the legibility of the food as to whether they can eat or not amidst the critical phase of their life. The stark reality of hunger at the advent of partition can be perceived especially in the case of the refugees hailing from East Pakistan. An aroma of cooked rice began to fill the air which broke down all barriers of religion and caste because little children from all around gathered together and came closer. They were hungry-stricken, unclean and staring at the cooked food in order to mitigate their hunger. Whenever, the hungry children appeared before Kumudini, she refused to provide them food until her son completed eating his food. She says,

Now get out from here, you skeletons' scot. One of the hungry children's mother came to Kumudini and retorted to her appropriately: what do you think. Have we never seen rice in our life time. God knows how many such handcuffs we have fed crows and ducks with (Sen 265).

Kumudini finally distributed her food among the unfed hapless children. The interplay between individual and others relies in the mind of Kumudini. Initially though she denied to give them food, finally being driven by her 'ethical responsibility', she shared her food with the unfed children. Thus such approach denies the otherisation emanating from the caste and class. Hunger dissolves all barriers and accentuates the chord of humanitarian aspect. Thus she shares an intimate space with them, it indicates a third space which refers to a kind of radical openness. It dismantles racial, social barrier, and opens up a heterogeneous space. Parashar did the same thing after looking at the ailing child who remained unfed and had been suffering from male nutrition. It restricted him from sucking her mother's breast milk. The hapless child stretched his hand to Parashar for the sake of help. The face of that child is incumbent upon his self in such a way that he took the responsibility of the child inspite of having his plenty of difficulties. His wife so proclaims, " You have picked up another poisonous thorn and brought him here"(Sen 268).

However, the lake which is contaminated with Cholera stricken people hardly allowed people to live in safely and on the other hand the sudden resonance of 'Alla ho' made their

inhabitation ephemeral, indicating their impending dissociation from the place they spent for few days. The echo of uncertainty kept on ringing repeatedly in their mind. Parashar thought “could these hordes of people who were leaving their own land and house for an unknown place, only to escape death, finally escape it?” (Sen 268). Parashar along with other people who were about to quit the place were confused and allowing their fortunes to the will of God. It becomes clear while a hapless man proclaims “Wherever God leads us”, we are moving to. The utmost uncertainty, pessimism, helplessness of the deracinated people hardly meet the Almighty who is supposed to retrieve them from the dungeon. Though Mohini met with Vaishnavi in the lake who had given her along with her child Jadav a place to live in but such turbulent atmosphere hardly allowed Vaishnavi's motto of humanity to have had permanent entity. So, the spatio-temporal dislocation of refugees in the story due to manifold reasons such as religion, caste, race tend to form a heterotopic space challenging the linearity of time and imagined physical space of a nation. They became ‘forever foreigner’ and refused to be a part of the cartographic domination of nation in post-partition time. The socially abjected refugees so joined in terra-incognita having no permanent root to settle down.

Jotirmayi Devi's ‘The Crossing’ reveals the deplorable condition of the Bengali Hindu emigrants who are forced to leave East Pakistan owing to religious persecution. Border crossing for the Bengali Hindu emigrants after the announcement of Partition is too difficult and horrible. Many of the emigrants including men in general and women in particular fell prey to the oppression of the border security force. The present story revolves around the pathetic story of the partition victims, Sudam and Durga. Both of them become insignificant and ‘dreg objects’ while Partition was announced. The conflicting emotion in relation to what their actual homeland is puts them in a confused zone as all of a sudden they have come to realize the morbid reality that their home no longer remains their home. With their bag and baggages they start their journey towards a new place by crossing the river. The border security forces seize everything what Sudam and Durga have. Sudam and Durga are the victims of circumstances. They are demanded to pay twenty-five rupees to have the permission to cross the border. In this connection, Sudam has to go to Kolkata to collect the money leaving his wife Durga under their control. Border Security forces' rapt attention to Durga with their vulnerable eyes is the premonition of her impending decay. Durga carries an epitome of morality which she will not allow to be wiped out. The otherisation in terms of gender has been prominent in the story which

as if provides them legitimacy to have a control on her body. The unrobing of Draupadi which affirms the stereotypical structure of patrimony in the ancient time finds its resonance with the border security forces attitude towards Durga in the story. It reduces her position to periphery. Understanding the possible harm upon Durga, Sudam goes to Saheb's house for the safe harbor of her wife. Meanwhile he will try to collect the required money. Durga under the care of Saheb's wife starts living in their house. Many a time she finds the desperation in the Security armies regarding her status, and concomitantly she feels that she has been an extra burden in their family. And the chance of handing her over to the armies is not undeniable. Hence, the anxiety of losing her chastity being a member of the Bengali Hindu community prevails in her mind. A kind of uncertainty and anxiety devours her on a daily basis while Sudam has not yet come after passing twenty-one days. She becomes suspicious about his arrival at all. Being overburdened with her future and the protection of her honour, she drowns herself in Ganga. It testifies to the stature of the Goddess Durga: her arrival and immersion. But Durga in the story hardly diminishes the miscreants, rather takes recourse to suicidal policy to ward herself off the vulnerable eyes of the patriarchy lest her chastity be compromised. This unfortunate incident points out how women are treated as objects, especially in the context of Partition. Woman body represents two important connotations: annihilation and contamination. The incident of raping the refugee women indicates the annihilation of women's body and of course connoting the contamination of women's parental race as it paves the path of producing 'hybridized child'. The honour, morality leads Durga to grab the thanatological discourse, testifying to how women are always seen as 'others'. As the lady is a refugee woman, she is usually treated as an animal. Thus having gone through the social abjection, she has been deprived of having her proper rights and treated as animals. Durga in a way appears as a dreg object and has been disinherited from the possibility of being human.

In conclusion, the socio-political turmoil that marked the 1950s, driven by religious persecution, forced countless Hindu families to seek refuge in Calcutta, a city already strained by overpopulation. The government's response, while initially supportive, became insufficient in addressing the growing crisis, leading to a dire economic and social situation. This compelled refugees to build their own camps, seeking survival in an environment that treated them as invisible and unwanted. Through the lens of Julia Kristeva's concept of abjection, we understand

how these refugees faced the brutal alienation of being neither fully part of their homeland nor accepted in their host country. Their experience, marked by constant marginalization and exclusion, reveals an enduring ambivalence—living "as others" and "with others." The refugees' bodies, symbolizing both the horrors of dislocation and the denial of their humanity, were treated as dehumanized waste, caught between the violence of sovereign power and the despair of their existence. The stories of characters like Jadav, Mohini, Sudam, and Durga underscore the profound emotional and physical toll of displacement. From caste divisions within their own community to the gendered violence inflicted on women, these narratives illuminate the harsh realities of refugees' lives. Yet, moments of shared humanity—such as the collective sharing of food or the bond formed amidst suffering—offer a glimmer of hope amidst despair. Ultimately, these stories challenge the notion of national identity and emphasize the need for empathy and solidarity beyond borders, urging us to reconsider the politics of belonging in a world where millions remain displaced and abjected.

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